

Innovation in Mena region: descriptive analysis among firms of Mena region

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Abstract :

Nowadays with rapid changes in the business world, companies in the developed countries are increasingly including innovation as one of their strategies to ensure business expansion and profitability. This study examined the innovativeness of the firms in Mena region. The study utilized Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS) of the Mena region .

The finding shows that the maximum of the innovations is in firms level follows to low investment, risks and expenditures. Innovation in country level takes the second level after firm level follows the high levels of risks, expenditures. The latest rate of innovation is for the international level because of the high levels of risks, expenditures .

Also, majority of the firms of the Mena region are interested in marketing innovation and product innovation more than process innovation and organizational innovation. For marketing innovation, firms are interested in new methods of advertising and product promotion.

Keywords : Innovation , MENA Region, BEEPS Data.

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Introduction:

The roles of innovation in the expansion of industrial activities and the general performance of an economy have long been established by economists and historians since the 19th century industrial revolution. Innovation commitment by a country or a firm is often conceptualized as one of the important determinants of micro-level productivity gains and macro-level level economic growth (Acemoglu 2009; Cohen et Levinthal 1989; Joseph Alois Schumpeter 1961). Different underdeveloped countries start following the developed countries in the field of innovation. Following the research paper of (Bourouaha et Maliki 2018), the underdeveloped African countries starts following the developed countries focusing on different factors that enforce the innovativeness. Different example of African countries is launching procedures in the way of fostering innovation such as Rwanda, Gambia, Malawi and Mozambique .

In addition, some of MENA countries are interested in innovation as the way of interring to the international market

Following the high rate of changes in the technology and the environment, in addition to the mixture factors that play key roles in the future forecast of the enterprise and the instable competitiveness due to the new competitors, it is very important for the enterprise to respond to this change and to survive to keep their rate of market. From the most important factors that firms could invest to survive for a long period is to innovate.

Therefore, the paper is organized as follows: first introduction, literature review for innovation types, levels of innovation and kinds of innovation. Next section, exploratory study for the innovation in the Mena region. In the end, the study finish with a conclusion that contain the results of empirical research.

1. Literature review:

1.1. Innovation: Definition and importance:

Following the new appearance of innovation, there are many studies and many authors tried to give a clear and global definition of innovation. From the first side and according to (Rennings 2000), "the source of innovation is the Latin word *Novus* which means new. It is referred sometimes as new idea, new method or new device or the process of creating something new. From another side , the Innovation is a continuous process (OECD 2005, 15). It is also defined following (Joel Clarke 2015, 1) as the act which endows resources with a new capacity to create wealth. Also, Innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations. Following the studies of (Pavitt et Walker 1976; Kim 1980; Archibugi, Cesaratto, et Sirilli 1991; Ernst et Kim 2002; Guan et Chen 2012), "the innovation could be defined also as major stimulus to national economic growth in the different categories of economies (industrial, newly industrialized and the developing economies)". Innovation is central to the growth of output and productivity. In the neoclassical view and according to (Sutton et Klein 2003) and (OECD 2005, 30) the innovation is an asset of creation, for that it is an aspect of business cycle .

The importance of the innovation characterized in different ways, where the new forms of innovation could be the drives of the economic development for all regions. According to (Nelson et Winter 1982), "the innovation is a path-dependent process whereby knowledge and technology are developed through interaction between various actors and other factors."

Innovation is defined also as a system emphasizes the importance of the transfer and the diffusion of ideas, skills, knowledge, information and the signals of many kinds between persons, activities and department in the society and indeed in the organizations. It can be defined also as a dynamic process in which knowledge is

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accumulated through learning and interaction. From this latest definition, the diffusion of knowledge between workers seems from the important ways that foster the innovation in the organization .

According to (Bhidé 2006),” From the important factor that it enhances the enterprise to innovation in the side of the entrepreneurial activity and the research and development policies, the willingness of the customer to try, discover and use the new products and services which it called also ‘Venturesome consumption”.

1.2. Levels of innovation:

There are different characteristics to select the levels of the innovations. There are two separated sides to select the different levels of innovation. The first side is the one of firm. This latest show that most appeared character is the levels of innovation of product or service in the market. Following the report of (OECD 2009, 12), there are three level of innovation:

a) New to the firm:

This level of innovation includes all new things such as procedures, technics ...etc. these new things were in the market and in the other enterprises but new in our enterprises .

b) New to the market:

This level contains the new things for our market, but it was exit in the other market

c) New to the world:

It is the most important level because it brings new things that did not exist before.

However, the second side is concerning the product itself. Following the research of (Kris Miner 2010), there are four levels of innovation :

Level one: this level emphasizes minimal changes to existing products, a low amount of new investments and very low risk.

Level two: integrating new features into existing products on the market or creating differential versions of the same new products to sell to various demographic groups.

Level three: this level could be described as evolutionary development, it is characterized by the high financial investments and high levels of risks with large payoff.

Level four: this level is described by the revolutionary development, the existence of high levels of risks than other, large investments in addition to limitless payoffs to achieve the fixed goals.

1.3. Kinds of innovation:

Many studies mention the three kinds of innovation such as (Dodgson et Gann 2010):

1.3.1. Incremental innovation:

The incremental innovation characterized in the new improvement that are coming from new ideas, to an existing product, service or even a process of execution.

1.3.2. Breakthrough innovation:

These kinds of innovation appear when the innovative product enter to a new market.

1.3.3. The radical (transformational) Innovation:

We say that this is a Radical Innovation where the nature of the product service or the process was completely changed.

To explain these two previous parts for the innovation (levels, kinds), the figure below represents the both of levels and kinds of innovation and show the relationship between them:

Figure 1: kinds of innovation

source: edited by the authors

1.4. Types of innovation:

There are four types of innovation segmented to two different types, technological innovation and non-technological innovation. Starting with the technological innovation, there will be two types of innovation that they use technology:

1.4.1. Technological innovation:

According to (Krishnaswamy, Mathirajan, et Bala Subrahmanya 2014), the activities use technology according to its important in innovation. Because, there are the activities that it uses technology, so in this time we will find technological innovation, that is mean we use technology to innovate. Therefore, we will see touch this kind of innovation in two places, the product or service from a side and the process of producing the product or giving the service.

1.4.1.1. Product innovation:

In the way of bringing innovation into the level of the product, the innovation in the product will be realized in following some important procedures (Cheng, Chang, et Li 2013). In the first, we find that improving in technical specification as design, this kind of improvement need technology. To compare it with the kinds of innovation, we find that this is one of the incremental innovations because it keeps the characteristics of the product. From the important ways of innovation that are used in the level of

product is by improving the component and materials. Using an incorporated software from the important technological innovation used in the level of the product for the result of innovating the product.

1.4.1.2. Process innovation:

In a hand, the process innovation characterized in the different procedures used to achieve the innovation in the process of the production (Ivanov et Avasilcăi 2014). From the second hand, the innovation did not focus just in the product, but for all the processes of the creation from the idea to the ways of selling the product or service .

In this point, we can find three important point of the product or process innovation as it shown below:

a- Changes in techniques:

These techniques characterized in the different changes in the process, these technics may be will reduce from the consumption of the energy, reduce the time of the process pf production or distribution.

b- Changes in equipment:

With using new equipment for the procedure of innovation and these, equipment's will be of course equipment's with high technology.

c- Changes in software:

From the newest method of implementing innovation in the enterprise is following the technological development and changes and using new software that will facilitate any procedure that was take many times to be executed in a short time with less consumption of energy and raw material with a high quality and less level of wastes.

1.4.2. Non-technological innovation:

Innovation does not include just technologically new products and processes but also improvements in areas such as logistics, distribution and marketing. The second part are the activities that it does not use technology According to (Hyard 2013), so it is not technological innovation, and we will touch this kind of innovation in both of

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organizational and marketing innovation. Why? because it does need technology in the activity. From this point, we can suggest, there will be a clarification in the meaning of the innovation, where in the first, we think that innovation is always related with technology, so in the activities that it does not use technology machines or materials; we cannot think that it will be able to be innovated.

To more clarify the different types of the innovation and what they need to be innovated, the figure bellow presents this context in two different types of innovation separated in the term of using technology, so there will be technological innovation and non-technological innovation. These two types of innovation will be divided to the number of types supposed for each type.

For the non-technological innovation, we found there are two other types of innovation that did not need technology to be innovated. These are:

1.4.2.1. Marketing innovation:

According to (Halpern 2010), Marketing is an important activity for the enterprises, according to its role from the creation of the product until selling it. In addition, by using innovated method as it shown in the figure bellow, it will be an innovated activity or marketing innovation.

Figure 2: Innovation and four Ps

source:(OECD 2005)

These innovated activities could be segmented through the four Ps as it shown above in addition to use other new methods such as:

- Implementing new marketing method,
- Involving significant changes in products,
- Involving changes in promotion, pricing ... etc.

1.4.1.1. Organizational innovation:

According to the different exchanges between enterprise and organization, the organization get an important role in the performance on the enterprise (Camisón et Villar-López 2014). According to (Laforet 2013), the organizational innovation has a greater impact on the small and medium sized enterprises.

2. Results and discussion:

The purpose of this research is to look for the real state of innovation in the firms of the MENA region. in addition, the research sought to discover the different types of innovation in the region, what are the main reasons that push the firms to innovate, and what are the main ways followed to innovate.

2.1. Characteristics of the sample:

The sample of the study contain 6566 firms from the MENA region (using data of Beeps database). The table below presents the distribution of the firms per region of activity. In the sample, there is mixture of regions where maximum of firms situated in Egypt with 2897 firms (that it represent 44.1% of the sample). The Map. 1 presents the distribution of the firms of sample per countries of MENA region. This result follows the willingness of the managers of the firms to share information in the aim of developing their firms following the feedback of information (that is the exploitation of the data from the scientist).

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Table 1. Characteristics of the firms

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage(N=6566)
Country	Palestine	434	6,6
	Morocco	407	6,2
	Egypt	2897	44,1
	Yemen	353	5,4
	Lebanon	561	8,5
	Djibouti	266	4,1
	Israel	483	7,4
	Tunisia	592	9,0
	Jordan	573	8,7
Size	Micro	28	0.4
	Small	3122	47.5
	Medium	2258	34.4
	Large	1155	17.6
	Don't know	3	0.0

Source: edited by the authors

The second characteristics presented in the table is the size of the firms. The data shows the mixture of the sizes of firms (all sizes of firms mentioned) but with different rates. In the first, small sized firms with 3122 firms (that it represents 47.5% of the sample).

Where In the second rate, we find medium sized firms take second rates with 2258 (that it represents 34.4% of the sample). The large sized firms take the thirds place in the sample with 1155 large firms (that it represents 17.6% of the sample). However, the micro sized firms represent just 0.4% of the sample of the study. These data show that the entrepreneurs of the MENA region are more interested in creating small sized firms. This latest is following the entrepreneurial procedures and facilities offered to individuals to create their own firms such as financial mechanisms created in Algeria

to foster entrepreneurship and curb unemployment (Bourouaha et Maliki 2014, 2005-12).

Map. 1: distribution of the firms on the map of MENA region

Source: edited by the author

To test the innovativeness of the firms, table 2 presents the distribution of the firms of the MENA region per innovation. As it presented below, 44 % of our sample are innovative firms.

Table 2: Repartition of firms per innovation

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	2889	44,0
No	3677	56,0
Total	6566	100,0

Source: edited by the author using BEEPS data

These results mention that just few of the firms of MENA region are interested in innovation. However, more than half of the firms (that is 3677 firms of 6566) are not innovative firms. This latest is because of different causes. Following (Bourouaha et Bouredja 2017, 132; OECD 2005, 113), there are different causes that hamper

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enterprises to innovate. These causes are related from another way with the types of innovation. These causes concern the factors of cost, knowledge market and institutional. Therefore, following the high risk of innovation, the high costs to innovate, low levels of skills and knowledge of the employees, the inability of the market to accept new innovative product in addition to the lack of institution such as infrastructures. All these causes do not encourage firms in the Mena region to innovation.

Following the different types of innovation presented in the theoretical parts, the maximum operations of the firms have their parts of innovation (that is product, marketing, organization and process). And these operations are related in the firm, but different in the activity. Therefore, the following points contain descriptive analysis of different types of innovation in the Mena region.

2.2. Product innovation:

The product innovation is among the technological innovation, it is concerning all improvement or changes existed in the product. Therefore, to analyze the innovativeness of the product, four questions are interested for the product innovation. The first question is as follows:

Question 01: what is the difference between new and old product?

This question concerns the innovative firms in the field of product. It explains the main differences between the existed product that is new and innovative product and old product. Following data presented in Table 3, 74.6% of the firms add new functions to an existing product, that is keep some characteristics and adding new function. In the second rate, 62.6% of the firms answer that the new product is completely new to the firms.

Table 3: Difference between innovative and old product (multi-responses)
(innovation product)

type of Innovation Product	N(1557)	%	% of Cases
New product has added new functions to an existing product	1162	20,00%	74.6%
New product is completely new to the firm	975	16,80%	62.6%
New product has completely new functions compared to the existing product	954	16,40%	61.3%
New product looks different from the existing product	727	12,50%	46.7%
New product uses new materials or components that enhance its performance	668	11,50%	42.9%
New product uses new technology	615	10,60%	39.5%
New product/service: More efficient/easier to use	335	5,80%	21.5%
New product is cheaper to produce compared to the existing product	330	5,70%	21.2%
Other	53	0,90%	3.4%
Total	5819	100,00%	373.7%

Source: edited by the author using BEEPS data

However, 61.3% firms where, there new product has completely new functions in comparing with the old one. From the packaging side, 46.7% of the firms mention that the new product looks different from the existing one such as color, style of packaging ...etc. Also, from the main points that push the firms to innovate is the performance of product. Therefore, 42.9% of the innovative firms are using new materials in the way of enhancing the performance of the product, 21.5% of the innovative firms are innovating to make the product more efficient and easier to use. However, just 21.2% of these firms mention that the new innovative product is cheaper comparing with the previous product.

After discovering that maximum innovative firms mention that they add new function to the existing product in the first rate, where the second rate is that the new

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product is completely new to the firm. The second question is concerning the way of improving the product.

Question 02: How the main new or significantly improved product was introduced or developed?

As it mentions in Table 4 below, 60.8% innovative firms are developing the new product by themselves. This latest result explain that the firms of the Mena region feel afraid of losing the innovative idea according to competition, the firms do not like to share the information about its activity, low level or inexistence of intellectual property right of the firms. In addition, the low level of technology and skills of these region oblige the firms to develop itself alone. Therefore, majority of the innovative firms develop their product by themselves.

Table 4: different Ways for product innovation

Ways of product innovation	Frequency (1557)	Valid%
Developed or adapted by this firm	947	60,8
Developed in cooperation with suppliers from abroad	159	10,2
Developed in cooperation with domestic client firms	109	7
Licensed products or services from another firm	83	5,3
Developed in cooperation with domestic suppliers	83	5,3
Developed in cooperation with client firms from abroad	56	3,6
Introduced the firm own version of a product or service	54	3,5
Developed in cooperation with external academic or research institute	15	1
Other	37	2,4
Don't know	14	0,9
Total	1557	100,0

Source: edited by the author using BEEPS data

To select the source of innovation, the Table 5 below presents the answers of the innovative firms for the question below:

Question 03: in comparison between the improved production or delivery method and previously methods used by the firm. Did it require significant changes in: techniques, machinery and equipment, software or management?

From the important changes happened in the firm with the aim of improving performance, productivity and innovation of the product are making changes in the process that it follows. This latest touch all of techniques applied in the production, the equipment and software's used in the production in addition the management methods follows. The data of Table 5 present the distribution of the innovative firms per changes required for product innovation. First, 77.1% of innovative firms mention that the product innovation requires changes in machinery and equipment. In the second place, 71.4% of innovative firms mention in the second place the changes in techniques of production for the product to be innovated. Changes required in the software's takes the third place where 50.1% innovative firms mention the importance of changes in software's of the product innovation. In the last rates, 47.6% firms require changes in management for the innovation product.

Table 5: Significant changes required in production or delivery method to be innovated

Changes	N(1557)	%	% of Cases
Significant changes in Techniques	1112	29,0%	71,4%
Significant changes in Machinery and equipment	1200	31,3%	77,1%
Significant changes in Software	780	20,3%	50,1%
Significant changes in Management	741	19,3%	47,6%
Total	3833	100,0%	246,2%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Source: edited by the author using Beeps data

2.3. Process innovation:

The second technological type of innovation is the process innovation, i.e. the innovation in different processes of the firms. To measure the aims of the firms after

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the innovation process, Table 6 summarize the goals of innovation process for the innovative firms by answering question 04 below.

Question 04: does any of the following describe why this firm introduced the main new or significantly improved process?

Starting from different goals of the firms, the satisfaction of the market desirous is the first goals of innovating the process by raising the volume of the production, where 88.2% innovative firms in the process, mention that they innovate the process in the way of raising the volume of the production or offering more services. After producing more, surviving in the market and keeping up with the competitors takes the second place with 87.7% of innovative firm that innovate their process for these goals. Raising the quality also has its parts among the goals with rate of 85.2% of innovative firms of innovation process

Also, the goal of reducing the cost of production is following the difference between old and innovative product (i.e. in general, the innovative product is expensive than the old product).

Table 6: the goals of the innovation process

Different goals of innovation process	N(1337)	%	% of Cases
To raise the volume of products sold or services offered	1352	14,5%	88,2%
To keep up with competition	1344	14,4%	87,7%
To raise the quality of products sold or services offered by this firm	1306	14,0%	85,2%
To open up new markets or increase market share	1233	13,2%	80,4%
To raise the flexibility or speed of selling products or offering services	1209	13,0%	78,9%
To extend the range of products sold or services offered by this firm	1188	12,8%	77,5%
To comply with regulations or standards	983	10,5%	64,1%

To lower the cost of production or offering services	701	7,5%	45,7%
Total	9316	100,0%	607,7%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Source: edited by the author using Beeps data

Comparing between the old and innovative process by answering question 05, Table 7 presents the distribution of innovative firms and the field of comparison between the processes.

Question 05: In what aspects is the main new or significantly improved process different from the original?

Following data presented Table 7, there are in general four fields of comparison between old and innovative process that are related with the time, cost, automation and machinery. Starting with the definition of a process that is series of action or steps taken in order to achieve a particular end. So, it is related in the first with time. Therefore, high rates of innovative firms (85.5%) mention that the innovation process is faster than the old one. That is means, the first matter of innovating the process is reducing time of production, or offering services. Reducing time of production provide more production in same time as before, that will reduce cost of employment, exploitation of machines. This latest will provide costs less than the ones before. Therefore, second field of comparison is cost, 55.9% of innovative firms mention that the costs with new process is less than the cost of the old process. Process innovation is among the technological types of innovation, so technology has its effect on it. Therefore, third field is the automation of the process, where 53% of innovative firms mention that the innovative process is more automated partially or fully. Following the technological development, and using new machines. The firms have to improve their process in the aim of following the technological level of the machines. Therefore, 51% of innovative firms are innovating their process to complement their machinery of production.

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Table 7: Comparison between old and innovative process

comparison between old and innovative process	N(1337)	%	% of Cases
It is faster than the old process	1143	33,5%	85,5%
It lowers costs compared to the old process	747	21,9%	55,9%
It automates manual processes partially or fully	709	20,8%	53,0%
It complements new machinery	682	20,0%	51,0%
Other aspects	130	3,8%	9,7%
Total	3411	100,0%	255,1%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Source: edited by the author using Beeps data

2.4. Organizational innovation:

In the second side of technological innovation, the non-technological innovation has its part also in the firms. It touches as it presented above both organizational and marketing innovation. For the organizational innovation, it includes different changes happened for the good organization of the firm. Therefore, to measure the organizational innovation in the firms of Mena region, Table 8 presents the data of the firms that answer question 06 below:

Question 06: Did this firm, introduce new or significantly improved organizational methods in the following areas for the first time?

Following data presented in Table 8 bellow, high rates of innovative firms with 76.6% are implementing organizational innovation by implementing new methods for distributing responsibilities and decision making among employees. In the second rate, 65.6% of innovative firms are implementing the organizational innovation by implementing new systems to better use or exchange information, knowledge and skills. These two previous ways are related with the human capital in general; however, the next two ways are related with management structure and management systems with 63.7% and 60.9% of innovative firms respectively. For the latest two ways of organizational innovation, the firms have implemented ways that are related

with the outside of the firms, by launching new types of activities. For these ways, 39.3% of innovative firms in organization launch new types of collaborations to achieve their goals. However, following (Aubert, Kishore, et Iriyama 2015; Bourouaha et Bouredja 2016), communication presents the important role of outsourcing for entrepreneurship and innovation. Therefore, the last rate is for the 35.5% of innovative firms that using outsourcing with other firms as way for their organizational innovation.

Table 8: Ways of organizational Innovation in the firms

Ways of organizational Innovation	N(1286)	%	% of Cases
New methods for distributing responsibilities & decision making among employees	985	22,4%	76,6%
New systems to better use or exchange information, knowledge, skills	844	19,2%	65,6%
A significant change to the management structure	819	18,6%	63,7%
Introduction of management systems for general production or supply operations	783	17,8%	60,9%
New types of collaborations	505	11,5%	39,3%
Outsourcing or subcontracting of business activities	457	10,4%	35,5%
Total	4393	100%	341,6%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1

Source: edited by the author using Beeps data

2.5. Marketing innovation:

In addition to the organizational innovation as one of the non-technological innovation in the firms, marketing innovation takes the second parts following its importance for the firm. Table 9 presents the answers of innovative firms for the question 07 below:

Question 07: according to you, did this firm introduce new or significantly improved marketing methods in the in the following areas for the first time?

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At the beginning, Table 9 summarizes the four pillars of marketing that are: Price, Place, Product and Promotion. Therefore, the marketing innovation will touch directly these four pillars. Following data presented in the table, introducing new methods of advertising and product promotion takes the first places from the four pillars of the marketing innovation with 70.5% of innovative firms. Second rate is for the new pricing strategies implemented by 63.1% of innovative firms. In the third place, distribution and sales channels with 58.8%. This mean that the innovative firms are interested in innovating the ways of promotion in the degree, the pricing strategies in second degree and distribution as third degree. However, the appearance of the product takes the fourth place where 49.8% of innovative firms are making changes on the product as a marketing pillar.

Table 9: Faces of marketing innovation in MENA firms

Faces of marketing innovation	N (2687)	%	% of Cases
Introduction of a new method of advertising and product promotion	907	29,1%	70,5%
New pricing strategies to market the firm's goods or services	811	26,1%	63,1%
Introduction of a new method of product placement or sales channels	756	24,3%	58,8%
Significant changes in the product's appearance	641	20,6%	49,8%
Total	3115	100,0%	242,2%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Source: edited by the author using Beeps data

After analyzing the different types of innovation for the Mena region, Table 10 presents the distribution of innovative firms per types of innovation. Marketing innovation take the first rates among the innovative firms with 93% of innovative firms. these means that the innovative firms of the Mena region are interested a lot in

developing their marketing with the aim of augmenting benefits, satisfying their desirous and the needs of the customers. In addition, product innovation takes the second rates with 53.9% of innovative firms. these latest shows that the innovative firms are interested in the second rate with the development of their product following the different variables of the market such as technological level of the market, the style and packaging desired in the market in addition to the competition ... etc. Also, following the two previous types of innovation, innovation process takes the third place with 44.5% of innovative firms.

Table 10: different types of innovation in the firm (multiple response)

types of innovation in the firm ^a	N	%	% of obs
New improved methods of manufacturing products or offering service (product innovation)	1557	22,7%	53,9%
New improved supporting activities for your processes (process innovation)	1337	19,4%	46,2%
New improved organizational structures or management practices (organizational innovation)	1286	18,7%	44,5%
New improved marketing methods (marketing innovation)	2687	39,1%	93%
Total	6867	100,0%	237,7%

a. Groupe de dichotomies mis en tableau à la valeur 1.

Source: edited by the author using BEEPS data

However, the organization does not matter maximum of firms, therefore, just 44.5% of innovative firms are interested in organizational innovation.

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Figure 3: Repartition of innovative firms in MENA region per types of innovation

Source: edited by the author

2.6. Levels of innovation:

Starting from the theoretical parts, there are three levels of innovation that are new to the firm, new to the market, and new to the world. Therefore, the last part of the study is to analyze the levels of innovation of the MENA firms.

Table 11 below presents the repartition of the innovation firms per levels of innovation:

Table 11: Levels of innovation

levels of innovation ^a	N	%	%of obs
The improved product was new to: this firm's local market	2583	48,7%	89,4%
The improved product was new to country	1996	37,6%	69,1%
The improved product was new to: International market	725	13,7%	25,1%
Total	5304	100,0%	183,6%

a. Groupe de dichotomies mis en tableau à la valeur 1.

Source: edited by the author using BEEPS data

Following the different efforts of the firms to develop their products, services, processes, organizations ...etc. there will be new innovative results for the firms. Therefore, the high rates of these results are focused on the local market level with

89.4%. This rate is due to the local efforts of the firms in different types of innovation such as new advertising methods for marketing, the new methods of distributing responsibilities as organizational innovation ...etc. This level of innovation characterized with low level of risks, low costs with minimum changes in the product, service or process ...etc. For the second level, 69.1% of the innovative firms have innovation in the level of country, i.e. the new improvement is new in all the country. This latest is due to the efforts and new expenditures in the field, with the aim of developing and innovating. The country level takes the second places following obstacles and barriers faced because it is difficult to improve something new in the country level following cost, level of knowledge and skills. However, the innovation in the international market level needs special characteristics as large investments with high costs, special knowledge and skills with high risks. Therefore, just 25.1% of innovative firms of Mena region are innovating in international level.

Conclusion:

The principal objective of this study was the examination of the innovation in the firms of Mena region using the Beeps dataset. After analyzing the sample, maximum of the firms examined situated in middle east of the region. More than the half of the examined firms are not interested in innovation with 44% are innovative firms against 56% that are not innovative firms. The four types of innovation faced are product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation and organizational innovation with 53.9%, 46.2%, 93% and 44.5% respectively. These distribution mention that majority of innovative firms implement marketing innovation against other types of innovation. These types are segmented into two types that are technological and non-technological innovation. For the technological innovation, there are innovation product and innovation process. For the innovation product, maximum of the firm's innovator in the innovation product adding new functions to an existing product to be innovated, where price takes the last rate, following the costs

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of investment. Therefore, it is rarely to find innovated product cheaper than the old product. These innovations are adapted by different ways where 60.8% of the innovative firms in the product innovation are developing their innovation by theme selves. The product innovation could be adapted following different changes, where maximum of innovative firms in the product innovation mention the requirement of significant changes in machinery and equipment with 77.1% and in techniques with 71.4% of innovative firms to innovate. For the innovation process, this type of innovation is implemented by the firms of Mena region for different goals such as raising the volume of product sold or services offered, keeping with competition and raising the quality of product sold or services offered. After comparison between the improved and old process, the results show that 85.5% of the firms found difference in time, where 55.9% found difference in costs. For the non-technological innovation, organizational innovation is implemented in the Mena firms by using different organizational methods. 76.6% of innovative firms in organization are using new methods for distribution of responsibilities and 65.6% implement new system to better use information, skills and knowledge. For the second non-technological innovation types, marketing innovation has its part among innovative firms in Mena region. 70.5% of innovative firms are interested in innovation marketing by implementing new methods of advertising and product promotion. Second rates of innovative firms interested in pricing strategies as marketing innovation. For the innovation levels of the firms, 89.4% of the innovated firms are in firms' levels due to the low risks, low costs of investment. With the augmentation of innovation level (firm, country, international), there is reduction in the innovative firms (selection) following augmentation in risks, high expenditures, special skills and knowledge...etc.

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